

TEACHERS' CONCERNS ABOUT INCLUSIVE EDUCATION**Kumud Gaur¹, Ph.D. , Shashi Malik², Ph.D. & Indrani Verma³, Ph.D.**¹*Post Doctoral Fellow (UGC), Dept. of Education, V.M.L.G. College, Ghaziabad.*²*Assistant Professor, Dept. of Education, V.M.L.G. College, Ghaziabad.*³*Associate Professor, HOD, Dept. of Education, V.M.L.G. College, Ghaziabad.***Abstract**

This paper is an attempt to find the difference between the concerns of Govt. aided and Self financed college teachers toward the inclusion of students with disabilities into general education classrooms. Participants included 80 college teachers. The CIES, Concerns about Inclusive Education Scale (Sharma & Desai, 2002), were utilized to determine participants' level of concern about the inclusion of students with disabilities into mainstream settings.

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Introduction

UNICEF's Report on the Status of Disability in India 2000 states that there are around 30 million children in India suffering from some form of disability. The Sixth All-India Educational Survey (NCERT, 1998) reports that of India's 200 million school-aged children (6–14 years), 20 million require special needs education. While the national average for gross enrolment in school is over 90 per cent, less than five per cent of children with disabilities are in school.

Understanding the Difference: Inclusive, integrated and Segregated Education:-

Segregated education occurs when students with disabilities learn completely separate from their peers¹. often, especially in “developing” countries, segregated education takes place in the form of special schools created specifically for the education of students with disabilities, or in completely separate classrooms for students with disabilities. Segregated education pinpoints the child as the problem in the system, the impediment to learning, and as a result, these students

will often receive a completely different curriculum and different methods of testing, rather than being taught the same curriculum as their peersⁱⁱ. This separation in school often creates separation within other areas of life as well.

Integrated education is similar to inclusive education, but without any ideological commitment to equity. Integration places students in a mainstream classroom with “some adaptations and resourcesⁱⁱⁱ.” However, students are expected to “fit in with pre-existing 3 structures, attitudes and an unaltered environment^{iv}.” Integration is often mistaken for inclusion because students are placed in a mainstream classroom, which is a step towards inclusion. However, if there has not been a paradigm shift within the school and these students are not perceived as equals, if curriculum is not taught for the understanding of all instead of some, then the students are integrated, but not included in the school.

Inclusive education “is a process of strengthening the capacity of the education system to reach out to all learners^v.” “It involves restructuring the culture, policies and practices in schools so that they can respond to the diversity of students in their locality^{vi}.”

Inclusive education means that all children, regardless of their ability level, are included in a mainstream classroom, or in the most appropriate or least restrictive environment (LRE), that students of all ability levels are taught as equals, and that teachers must adjust their curriculum and teaching methodologies so that all students benefit^{vii}. Inclusion is about making sure that each and every student feels welcome and that their unique needs and learning styles are attended to and valued.

Training teachers in teaching methods that include students of all ability levels, as well as spreading awareness to teachers about the importance and benefits of inclusion, is one of the most important parts of implementing a system of inclusive education, because the teachers are the people on-the-ground who are going to accommodate the students.

This paper is an attempt towards finding that is there any difference between the concerns of Govt. aided and self financed college teachers towards inclusive education.

Research Question

- 1) Is there any significant difference in the concerns of Govt.aided and Self financed college teachers?

Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the concerns of Govt. aided and Self financed colleges teachers about Inclusive Education.

Method: Present study was carried on the lines of descriptive survey.

Population

All the college teachers of Ghaziabad city constituted the population.

Sample

80 college teachers were selected through simple random technique to be included in the sample.

Tool

The tool, which explored teachers' concerns regarding the inclusion of students with disabilities into mainstream settings, was developed by Sharma and Desai (2002). The Concerns about Inclusive Education scale (CIE), contained 21 items and was designed to establish teachers' concerns regarding the inclusion of students with disabilities into regular classrooms. Each concern is worded as a single statement, tagged by a Likert-type classification, with responses varying from *Extremely Concerned* (4) to *Not Concerned at All* (1) (Sharma & Desai, 2002). A teacher's composite score on the CIES, could range from 21 to 84. This score is obtained by adding all the responses for each item. A higher score reflects a higher degree of concern regarding the inclusion of students with disabilities into mainstream classes while a low score may reflect lower levels of concern. The coefficient alpha for the total scale was 0.91, indicating that the scale has good internal consistency.

Result and discussion

To test the null hypothesis Ho1 stating that there is no significant difference between the concerns of Govt. aided and self financed colleges teachers about Inclusive Education, t test was applied.

The table 1 shows the summary of result:

Table 1: Mean, S.D. and 't' value of Concern about Inclusive Education with respect to Type of Institution.

Concern_about_Inclusive_Education	Institution_Type	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	't' Value
Total_Score	Govt.aided	40	45.45	6.614	.312
	Self financed	40	44.93	8.349	

The above table shows that the 't' value .312 is not significant at .05 level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the concerns of Govt. aided and self financed college teachers about inclusive education. Therefore, null hypothesis Ho1 was accepted.

This finding is in contrast with the findings of (Yadav, Das, Sharma & Tiwari , 2015). They found that significant difference existed in teacher concerns whether they taught in government versus privately managed schools. The mean concern score for government school teachers was 32.76, and for private school teachers it was 38.09. This shows that private school teachers are more concerned than government school teachers. A t test was conducted to determine whether the observed difference was statistically significant. A t value (-3.173) was significant at 0.01 level of significance. This means that the observed difference in the teachers' concerns was statistically significant.

This can be because the attitudes of general educators or educators in a mainstream environment, towards students with disabilities are generally improving, probably as a result of the various policies and schemes of Government.

Conclusions

This paper is an attempt to find the difference between the concerns of Govt. aided and Self financed college teachers toward the inclusion of students with disabilities into general education classrooms. It was found that respondents had similar concerns about inclusive education. This can be because the attitudes of general educators or educators in a mainstream environment, towards students with disabilities are generally improving irrespective of their type of institution, probably as a result of the various policies and schemes of Government. On the basis of this study we can say that teachers should be made aware of resources that various government bodies provide to implement such acts (inclusive education) and thus reduce their anxiety levels and modify their attitudes in positive directions.

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